

108. NOVEL STRATEGIES FOR AGRONOMIC BIOFORTIFICATION OF FOOD CROPS BY USING *TRICHODERMA* BIOCONTROL AGENTS AND THEIR SECONDARY METABOLITES. R. Marra^{1,2}, R. Varlese², A. De Martino², F. Scognamiglio², N. Lombardi^{1,2}, F. Vinale^{1,2}, M. Ruocco^{1,2}, S. Lanzuise^{1,2}, G. Manganiello², A. Pascale², F. Lacatena², A. Djella², A. Piccolo², M. Lorito^{1,2}, S.L. Woo^{1,2}. ¹National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), Via Università 133, I-80055 Portici (NA), Italy. ²Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Napoli "Federico II", Via Università 100, I-80055 Portici (NA), Italy. E-mail: woo@unina.it

Lentil (*Lens culinaris*) is a crop of great agronomic and commercial interest widely used for human consumption worldwide. From a nutritional standpoint, lentils are an excellent source of micronutrients, particularly iron and zinc. Nutritional deficiencies of these elements are among the leading causes of MicroNutrient Malnutrition or "hidden hunger". The aim of this work was to use biocontrol fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* and their Secondary Metabolites (SMs) to augment the nutritional value, specifically increase iron and/or zinc content, in lentil plants. Up to 11 different strains and 3 SMs were tested. The bioformulations (strains and/or SMs) were applied under different conditions and in diverse combinations to lentil seeds and plants. The mineral content of some micronutrients (Fe, Zn, Ca, Cu and Mg) in lentil plants was determined by atomic absorption spectrometry in flame (FAAS). The combinations of *Trichoderma* seed treatments and watering to the soil of diverse strains or SMs had varying effects on lentil. Particularly regarding Fe content, we found that the best treatments were those consisting of SMs applied to the seeds and *Trichoderma* strains watered to the soil, singly or in combinations, particularly when Fe and Zn solutions were supplemented to the soil. The results obtained indicated that the application of selected *Trichoderma* strains or SMs can increase the nutritional value of foods by improving the absorption or assimilation of important minerals micronutrients, such as iron and zinc. This microbial biotechnology could be an effective strategy to overcome micronutrient deficiencies and improve human nutrition.

109. LEAF EXTRACT OF *MYRTUS COMMUNIS* AGAINST *PSEUDOMONAS SYRINGAE* pv. *ACTINIDIAE* (PSA). F. Mastrogianni¹, L. Gallipoli¹, M.E. Virili¹, G.M. Balestra¹, A. Tiezzi². ¹Department of Agriculture, Forests, Nature and Energy (DAFNE), University of Tuscia, Via San Camillo de Lellis s.n.c., I-01100 Viterbo, Italy. ²Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-food and Forest Systems (DIBAF), University of Tuscia, Via San Camillo de Lellis s.n.c., I-01100 Viterbo, Italy. E-mail: antoniot@unitus.it

Myrtus communis is a common plant used in traditional medicine for its antimicrobial and antibacterial properties. *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae* (Psa) is the pathogen that causes bacterial canker of *Actinidia*. Currently, Psa is the leading cause of economic losses and severe damages to kiwifruit crops in the world. One way to counteract bacterial diseases, as bacterial canker of *Actinidia*, is based on the use of natural substances that are also usable in organic farming. For this reason, the object of research was to test dried extract and molecular fractions of *M. communis*, against Psa. *Myrtus communis* leaves were collected from plants and air dried; dried leaves were reduced as dust and ethanol added for extraction for 50 min in the dark. The ethanol extract was then centrifuged, the pellet discarded and the supernatant dried by a nitrogen flow. The residue was dissolved in a solution of DMSO 10% in distilled water to a concentration of 20 mg mL⁻¹ and filtered through a 0.22 µm cellulose syringe filter. The tested extract, *in toto*, showed activity able to contrast the Psa growth. Subsequently, the extract was processed by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) in order to detect which fraction was active *vs.* Psa. Each fraction singularly

obtained didn't show any antibacterial activity. Thus, was showed that effectiveness towards Psa is probably attributable to a synergistic effect of the identified fractions.

110. VIRUS SURVEY AND SANITATION FOR THE RECOVERY OF ANCIENT AUTOCHTHONOUS APULIAN GRAPES. M. Morelli¹, S. Zicca², G. Bottalico², A. Campanale¹, M. Calderaro³, G. Donatelli², P. Saldarelli¹, V.N. Savino^{1,3}, P. La Notte^{1,3}. ¹National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection (IPSP), Via G. Amendola 122/D, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ²Department of Soil, Plant and Food Sciences (DiSSPA), University of Bari "Aldo Moro", Via G. Amendola 165/A, I-70126 Bari, Italy. ³Centre for Research, Experimentation and Education in Agriculture (CRSFA) "Basile Caramia", Via Cisternino 281, I-70010 Locorotondo (BA), Italy. E-mail: pierfederico.lanotte@ipsp.cnr.it

In the frame of the Apulian Regional project Re.Ge.Vi.P. ("Recovery of Apulian grape germplasm"), in which 152 ancient autochthonous grape biotypes and cultivars were identified, a survey was conducted to assess the presence and incidence of eight viruses regulated in the Italian certification system: *Grapevine virus A* (GVA), *Grapevine virus B* (GVB), *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus-1*, -2, -3 (GLRaV-1, -2, -3), *Grapevine fanleaf virus* (GFLV), *Grapevine fleck virus* (GFkV) and *Arabis mosaic virus* (ArMV). Dormant canes from 80 table and wine grape accessions were ELISA-tested prior to their introduction in a repository of Apulian native germplasm. A great deal (85%) of the tested mother plants resulted positive for single or multiple infections. GLRaV-3 was the most represented virus (71.3%), followed by GFkV (45%) and GVA (42.5%). The presence of infectious degeneration agents was limited to GFLV (28.8%). GLRaV-1 was detected in 22.5% of the vines, whereas other viruses had either a low incidence (GLRaV-2) or were absent (GVB, ArMV). Infected accessions were submitted to sanitation, through *in vitro* meristem tip culture, in combination with heat therapy. To test the efficacy of virus elimination, a pool of 119 plantlets, deriving from micropropagation of treated explants was analysed by RT-PCR. Successful virus elimination occurred in 79% of the sanitized plants. GFLV and GFkV, which were both still present in eight treated explants, and GVA, were the viruses most recalcitrant to eradication. Results of this study allowed the addition of a number of minor autochthonous grape cultivars to the Apulian grapevine germplasm collection, thus contributing to the conservation of the hitherto neglected agro-biodiversity of Apulia.

111. SCREENING *CAPSICUM* spp. FOR TOLERANCE TO A RESISTANCE-BREAKING STRAIN OF *TOMATO SPOTTED WILT VIRUS* BY ARTIFICIAL INOCULATION. M. Parisi¹, F. Di Dato¹, M. Minutolo², G. Festa¹, D. Alioto². ¹Agricultural Research Council – Experimental Institute for Horticulture (CRA-ORT), Via Cavallegeri 25, I-84098 Pontecagnano Faiano (SA), Italy. ²Department of Agricultural Sciences, University of Napoli "Federico II", Via Università 100, I-80055 Portici (NA), Italy. E-mail: mario.paris@entecra.it

Pepper (*Capsicum annuum*) and other *Capsicum* species are severely affected by *Tomato spotted wilt virus* (TSWV). The highly polyphagous nature of TSWV and the efficiency of transmission by thrips (*Frankiniella occidentalis*) lead to a severe spread of the virus. The most effective strategy for controlling the virus damages is the use of durable resistance genes. However, the frequent appearance of Resistance-Breaking (RB) strains that overcome the resistance conferred by *Tsw* gene, makes search of new viral resistance/tolerance sources necessary. In this work, an isolate of TSWV isolated from a commercial resistant pepper hybrid in Sele Valley,